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ROBOTOTEXNIKA MEXANIZMLARNING MAXSUSLIKLARINI
IZLASHDA MATRITSAVIY USULNING QO'LLANISHI

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu ishimizda, robototexnikada uchraydigan mexanizmlar o'zining harakatlanish siklida maxsus holatlarga tushadi. Ushbu ishda darajali geometriya usullari yordamida mexanizmning maxsusliklari topiladi va shu maxsuslikning lokal atrofida mexanizmning harakatlanish traektoriyasi hisoblanadi. Mexanizmlarning maxsus holatga tushishini bartaraf etish uchun ularning strukturasi to'liq o'rganishga to'g'ri keladi. Ushbu ish shu muammoni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan.

Robototexnikaning ko'pgina mexanizmlari yuqori erkinlik darajasiga ega. Bu holat esa o'z navbatida mexanizmning harakatlanishi natijasida maxsus holatlarning paydo bo'lishiga olib keladi. Maxsus holatlarning paydo bo'lishi mexanizm xususiyatining o'zgarishiga, yani uning buzilishiga olib keladi. Shuning uchun yaratiladigan robototexnik mexanizmlarning holat funksiyalarining maxsusliklarini o'rganish dolzarb masaladir.

Misol tariqasida to'rtburchakli gidrosilindirlik mexanizmining maxsus nuqta atrofida asimtotik yechimini qaraylik. Bunda A, O, B, C nuqtalar quyidagi koordinatalarga ega: $O(0,0)$, $A(x_1, y_1)$, $B(x_2, y_2)$, $C(a, 0)$ va $AB = d_1$, $BC = d_2$ ($d_1, d_2 > 0$) o'zgarimas kattaliklar, L - musbat o'zgaruvchi kattalik.

Qaralayotgan mexanizmning holat funksiyalarining bog'lanish tenglamalarini quyidagi ko'rinishga ega:

$$\begin{cases} g_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x_1^2 + y_1^2 = L^2 \\ g_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 = d_1^2 \\ g_3 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (a - x_2)^2 + y_2^2 = d_2^2 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

(1) sistemada 3 ta tenglama, 5 ta noma'lumdan iborat, bundan ko'rinadiki, $n = 2$ erkinlik darajasiga ega, ya'ni 2 erkinlik darajasiga ega bo'lgan mexanizmdan iborat.

(1) sistemaning quyidagicha 3×5 tartibli yakobi matritsasi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

$$J = 2 \begin{pmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 & -L \\ x_1 - x_2 & y_1 - y_2 & x_2 - x_1 & y_2 - y_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 - a & y_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Matritsaning 3-tartibli minorlari quyidagilar:

$$\begin{aligned} M_1 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_2 & y_1 - y_2 & x_2 - x_1 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 - a \end{vmatrix} & M_2 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_2 & y_1 - y_2 & y_2 - y_1 \\ 0 & 0 & y_2 \end{vmatrix} & M_3 &= \\ & 8 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & -L \\ x_1 - x_2 & y_1 - y_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} & M_4 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_2 & x_2 - x_1 & y_2 - y_1 \\ 0 & x_2 - a & y_2 \end{vmatrix} \\ M_5 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & 0 & -L \\ x_1 - x_2 & x_2 - x_1 & 0 \\ 0 & x_2 - a & 0 \end{vmatrix} & M_6 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & 0 & -L \\ x_1 - x_2 & y_2 - y_1 & 0 \\ 0 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \\ M_7 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ y_1 - y_2 & x_2 - x_1 & y_2 - y_1 \\ 0 & x_2 - a & y_2 \end{vmatrix} & M_8 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} y_1 & 0 & -L \\ y_1 - y_2 & y_2 - y_1 & 0 \\ 0 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \\ M_9 &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} y_1 & 0 & -L \\ y_1 - y_2 & x_2 - x_1 & 0 \\ 0 & x_2 - a & 0 \end{vmatrix} & M_{10} &= 8 \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & -L \\ x_2 - x_1 & y_2 - y_1 & 0 \\ x_2 - a & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Bundan: $M_1 = 8(x_2 - a)(x_2y_1 - x_1y_2)$, $M_2 = 8y_2(x_2y_1 - x_1y_2)$, $M_3 = 0$, $M_4 = 8x_1(x_2y_1 - x_1y_2 + a(y_2 - y_1))$, $M_5 = 8L(x_2 - x_1)(x_2 - a)$, $M_6 = 8L(x_2 - x_1)y_2$, $M_7 = 8y_1(x_2y_1 - x_1y_2 + a(y_2 - y_1))$, $M_8 = 8Ly_2(y_2 - y_1)$, $M_9 = 8L(y_2 - y_1)(x_2 - a)$, $M_{10} = L(x_1y_2 - y_1x_2 + a(y_1 - y_2))$.

Teorema. To'rtburchakli gidrosilindirlik mexanizm ikkinchi tur maxsuslikka erishmaydi.

Isbot. Shartga ko'ra mexanizm ikkinchi tur maxsuslikka erishishi uchun $\forall i$ lar uchun

$M_i = 0$ ($i = \overline{1,10}$) sharti bajarilishi zarur. Lekin bunday holat yuz bermaydi, chunki aniqlanishiga ko'ra $x_1 \neq x_2$, $L > 0$.

(4-chizma)

$$M_1 = M_2 = M_3 = M_9 = 0$$

(3-chizma)

$$M_1 = M_2 = 0$$

(6-chizma)

$$M_1 = M_5 = M_6 = M_9 = 0$$

(5-chizma)

$$M_7 = 0$$

(7-chizma)

$$M_2 = M_3 = M_6 = M_8 = 0$$

(8-chizma)

$$M_1 = M_2 = M_3 = M_4 = M_6 = M_7 = M_8 = M_9 = M_{10} = 0$$

(10-chizma)

$$M_2 = M_6 = M_8 = 0$$

(9-chizma)

$$M_1 = M_2 = M_4 = 0$$

Endi Nyuton ko'pyoqliklari usuli yordamida P^0 maxsus nuqtaning kichik atrofida (1) sistemaning parametrik yechimlarini izlaymiz. Bunda $P^0(x_1^0, x_2^0, 0, 0, L^0)$ (8-chizma.) (1) sistemada quyidagi koordinatalar almashtirishni olaylik.

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = x_1^0 + z_1 \\ x_2 = x_2^0 + z_2 \\ y_1 = z_3 \\ y_2 = z_4 \\ L = L_0 + z_5 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda z_i ($i = \overline{1,5}$) lar P^0 maxsus nuqtadan kichik chetlanishdir. Bu qiymatlarni (1) sistemaga qo'yib quyidagi sistemani hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{cases} g_1 \triangleq (x_1^0 + z_1)^2 + z_3^2 = (L_0 + z_5)^2 \\ g_2 \triangleq (x_2^0 + z_2 - x_1^0 - z_1)^2 + (z_4 - z_3)^2 = d_1^2 \\ g_3 \triangleq (a - x_2^0 - z_2)^2 + z_4^2 = d_2^2 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Tegishli hisoblashlarni bajarib hamda (1) sistema shartlarini hisobga olib, quyidagi sistemaga kelamiz:

$$\begin{cases} z_1^2 + 2x_1^0 z_1 + z_3^2 - 2L_0 z_5 - z_5^2 = 0 \\ z_1^2 + 2(x_1^0 - x_2^0)z_1 - 2z_1 z_2 + 2(x_2^0 - x_1^0)z_2 + z_2^2 + (z_4 - z_3)^2 = 0 \\ z_2^2 + 2(x_2^0 - a)z_2 + z_4^2 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Nyuton ko'pyoqliklari usulini qo'llab (3) sistema uchun quyidagi qisqartma sistemani olamiz.

$$\begin{cases} 2x_1^0 z_1 + z_3^2 - 2L_0 z_5 = 0 \\ 2(x_2^0 - x_1^0)(z_2 - z_1) + (z_4 - z_3)^2 = 0 \\ 2(x_2^0 - a)z_2 + z_4^2 = 0 \end{cases}$$

Bu sistemani yechib:

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= \frac{1}{2(a-x_2^0)} z_4^2 + \frac{1}{2(x_2^0-x_1^0)} (z_4 - z_3)^2 \\ z_2 &= \frac{z_4^2}{2(a-x_2^0)} \\ z_5 &= \frac{x_1^0}{2L_0(a-x_2^0)} z_4^2 + \frac{x_1^0}{2L_0(x_2^0-x_1^0)} (z_4 - z_3)^2 + \frac{1}{2L_0} z_3^2. \end{aligned}$$

Topilgan z_i ($i = \overline{1,5}$) larni qiymatlarini (2) sistemaga qo'yib (1) sistema uchun asimptotik yechimni olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= x_1^0 + z_1 = x_1^0 + \frac{1}{2(a-x_2^0)} z_4^2 + \frac{1}{2(x_2^0-x_1^0)} (z_4 - z_3)^2 + \dots, \\ x_2 &= x_2^0 + z_2 = x_2^0 + \frac{z_4^2}{2(a-x_2^0)} + \dots, \\ y_1 &= z_3 + \dots, \\ y_2 &= z_4 + \dots, \\ L &= L_0 + z_5 = L_0 + \frac{x_1^0}{2L_0(a-x_2^0)} z_4^2 + \frac{x_1^0}{2L_0(x_2^0-x_1^0)} (z_4 - z_3)^2 + \frac{1}{2L_0} z_3^2 + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

(1) sistema uchun topilgan (5) yechimlardan ko'rinadiki (8-chizma), mexanizm bunday maxsus holatdan har xil yo'nalish bo'yicha harakatlanishi mumkin va ularni bilib zarur hollarda maxanizmning maxsus holatlarini yo'qotish mumkin, ya'ni mexanizmning parametrlarini o'zgartirib maxsus holatlarga tushmasligini ta'minlash mumkin bo'ladi.

Misol-1. Uchburchakli gidrosilindirlik mexanizimning maxsus nuqta atrofida asimptotik yechimini qaraylik. Bunda A, O, B nuqtalar quyidagi koordinatalarga ega: $O(0,0), A(x_1, x_2), B(a, 0)$ va $OA = l$ o'zgarmas kattalik.

Qaralayotgan mexanizmning holat funksiyalarini algebraik shaklda yozamiz:

$$\begin{cases} f_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x_1^2 + x_2^2 = l^2 \\ f_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (x_1 - a)^2 + x_2^2 = x_3^2 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

(10) sistemada 2 ta tenglama, 3 ta noma'lumdan iborat, bundan ko'rinadiki, $n = 1$ erkinlik darajasiga ega, ya'ni 1 erkinlik darajasiga ega bo'lgan mexanizmdan iborat. (10) sistemaning yakobi matritsasi quyidagicha ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

$$J = 2 \begin{pmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & 0 \\ x_1 - a & x_2 & -x_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Matritsaning 2- tartibli minorlari 3 ta bo'lib ular quyidagilardir:

Bundan $M_1 = ax_2, M_2 = -x_1 x_3, M_3 = -x_2 x_3$, ekanligi va $M_1 = M_3 = 0$ minorlarning nolga aylanishi mos holda mexanizmning maxsus holatga tushishini anglatadi, ya'ni erkinlik darajasini yuqotishdir. Aga $x_3 = 0$ shart bajarilsa O, A va B nuqtalar bir to'g'ri chiziqda yotishini anglatadi. $x_2 = 0$ bo'lganda birinchi tur maxsus holatni ifodalaydi. Osongina aniqlash mumkinki barcha M_i lar bir vaqtda nolga aylansa ya'ni $M_i = 0$ ($i = \overline{1,3}$) shartlari bajarilsa berilgan mexanizm ikkinchi tur maxsuslikka erishadi.

Misol-2 Yana bir To'rtburchakli gidrosilindirik mexanizimning maxsus nuqta atrofida asimtotik yechimini qaraylik. Bunda A, O, B, C nuqtalar quyidagi koordinatalarga ega: $O(0,0), A(x_1, y_1), B(x_3, 0), C(x_2, y_2)$, va $OA = a, OC = b, BC = c$ ($b < a < c$) o'zgarmas kattaliklar, L - musbat o'zgaruvchi kattalik.

Qaralayotgan mexanizmning holat funksiyalarining bog'lanish tenglamalarini tuzamiz:

$$\begin{cases} g_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x_1^2 + y_1^2 = a^2 \\ g_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (x_1 - x_3)^2 + y_1^2 = L^2 \\ g_3 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (x_2 - x_3)^2 + y_2^2 = c^2 \\ g_4 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x_2^2 + y_2^2 = b^2 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

(11) sistemada 4 ta tenglama, 6 ta noma'lumdan iborat, bundan ko'rinadiki,

$n = 2$ erkinlik darajasiga ega, ya'ni 2 erkinlik darajasiga ega bo'lgan mexanizmdan iborat.

(11) sistemaning quyidagicha 4×6 tartibli yakobi matritsasi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

$$J = 2 \begin{pmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & y_1 & 0 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 & -L \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 - x_3 & y_2 & x_3 - x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 & y_2 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Matritsaning 4-tartibli minorlari quyidagilar:

$$M_1 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 - x_3 & y_2 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 & y_2 \end{vmatrix} \quad M_2 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & y_1 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 - x_3 & x_3 - x_2 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_3 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & y_1 & 0 & -L \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 - x_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad M_4 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & y_1 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 \\ 0 & 0 & y_2 & x_3 - x_2 \\ 0 & 0 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_5 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & y_1 & 0 & -L \\ 0 & 0 & y_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad M_6 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & y_1 & x_3 - x_1 & -L \\ 0 & 0 & x_3 - x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_7 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & 0 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 \\ 0 & x_2 - x_3 & y_2 & x_3 - x_2 \\ 0 & x_2 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad M_8 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & 0 & 0 & -L \\ 0 & x_2 - x_3 & y_2 & 0 \\ 0 & x_2 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_9 = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 & -L \\ 0 & x_2 - x_3 & x_3 - x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & x_2 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{10} = 16 \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_3 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 & -L \\ 0 & y_2 & x_3 - x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & y_2 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_{11} = 16 \begin{vmatrix} y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ y_1 & 0 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 \\ 0 & x_2 - x_3 & y_2 & x_3 - x_2 \\ 0 & x_2 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{12} = 16 \begin{vmatrix} y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ y_1 & 0 & 0 & -L \\ 0 & x_2 - x_3 & y_2 & 0 \\ 0 & x_2 & y_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_{13} = 16 \begin{vmatrix} y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ y_1 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 & -L \\ 0 & x_2 - x_3 & x_3 - x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & x_2 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{14} = 16 \begin{vmatrix} y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ y_1 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 & -L \\ 0 & y_2 & x_3 - x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & y_2 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_{15} = 16 \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_3 - x_1 & -L \\ x_2 - x_3 & y_2 & x_3 - x_2 & 0 \\ x_2 & y_2 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

Bundan: $M_1 = -16x_3^2y_1y_2$; $M_2 = 16x_2x_3y_1(x_2 - x_3)$; $M_3 = 0$;
 $M_4 = 16x_3y_1y_2(x_2 - x_3)$; $M_5 = 0$; $M_6 = 0$; $M_7 = 16x_1x_3y_2(x_1 - x_3)$;
 $M_8 = 16x_1x_3y_2L$; $M_9 = 16x_1x_2L(x_3 - x_2)$; $M_{10} = 16x_1y_2L(x_3 - x_2)$;
 $M_{11} = 16x_3y_1y_2(x_1 - x_3)$; $M_{12} = 16x_3y_1y_2L$; $M_{13} = 16x_2y_1L(x_3 - x_2)$;
 $M_{14} = 16y_1y_2L(x_3 - x_2)$; $M_{15} = 0$;

Teorema. To'rtburchakli gidrosilindirlik mexanizm ikkinchi tur maxsuslikka erishmaydi.

Isbot. Shartga ko'ra mexanizm ikkinchi tur maxsuslikka erishishi uchun $\forall i$ lar uchun $M_i = 0$ ($i = \overline{1,10}$) sharti bajarilishi zarur. Lekin bunday holat yuz bermaydi, chunki aniqlanishiga ko'ra $b \neq c$ va $L > 0$

Endi Nyuton ko'pyoqliklari usuli yordamida P^0 maxsus nuqtaning kichik atrofida (11) sistemaning parametrik yechimlarini izlaymiz. Bunda $P^0(x_1^0, x_2^0, x_3^0, 0, 0, L_0)$ (2-chizma.) (11) sistemada quyidagi koordinatalar almashtirishni olaylik.

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = x_1^0 + z_1 \\ x_2 = x_2^0 + z_2 \\ x_3 = x_3^0 + z_3 \\ y_1 = z_4 \\ y_2 = z_5 \\ L = L_0 + z_6 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Bu yerda z_i ($i = \overline{1,6}$) lar P^0 maxsus nuqtadan kichik chetlanishdir. Bu qiymatlarni (11) sistemaga qo'yib quyidagi sistemani hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{cases} g_1 \triangleq (x_1^0 + z_1)^2 + z_4^2 = a^2 \\ g_2 \triangleq (x_1^0 + z_1 - x_3^0 - z_3)^2 + z_4^2 = (L_0 + z_6)^2 \\ g_3 \triangleq (x_2^0 + z_2 - x_3^0 - z_3)^2 + z_5^2 = c^2 \\ g_4 \triangleq (x_2^0 + z_2)^2 + z_5^2 = b^2 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Tegishli hisoblashlarni bajarib hamda (11) sistema shartlarini hisobga olib, quyidagi sistemaga kelimiz:

$$\begin{cases} z_1^2 + 2x_1^0 z_1 + z_4^2 = 0 \\ (z_1 - z_3)^2 + 2(x_1^0 - x_3^0)z_1 - 2(x_1^0 - x_3^0)z_3 + z_4^2 - z_6^2 - 2L_0 z_6 = 0 \\ (z_2 - z_3)^2 + 2(x_2^0 - x_3^0)z_2 - 2(x_2^0 - x_3^0)z_3 + z_5^2 = 0 \\ z_2^2 + 2x_2^0 z_2 + z_5^2 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Nyuton ko'pyoqliklari usulini qo'llab (13) sistema uchun quyidagi qisqartma sistemani olamiz.

$$\begin{cases} 2x_1^0 z_1 + z_4^2 = 0 \\ 2(x_1^0 - x_3^0)z_1 - 2(x_1^0 - x_3^0)z_3 + z_4^2 - 2L_0 z_6 = 0 \\ 2(x_2^0 - x_3^0)z_2 - 2(x_2^0 - x_3^0)z_3 + z_5^2 = 0 \\ 2x_2^0 z_2 + z_5^2 = 0 \end{cases}$$

Bu sistemani yechib:

$$z_1 = -\frac{z_4^2}{2x_1^0}$$

$$z_2 = -\frac{z_5^2}{2x_2^0}$$

$$z_3 = \frac{x_3^0}{2x_2^0(x_2^0 - x_3^0)} z_5^2$$

$$z_6 = \frac{1}{2L_0} \left(\frac{x_3^0}{x_1^0} z_4^2 - \frac{x_1^0 x_3^0 - x_3^{02}}{x_2^{02} - x_2^0 x_3^0} z_5^2 \right)$$

Topilgan z_i ($i = \overline{1,6}$) larni qiymatlarini (12) sistemaga qo'yib (11) sistema uchun asimptotik yechimni olamiz:

$$x_1 = x_1^0 + z_1 = x_1^0 - \frac{z_4^2}{2x_1^0} + \dots,$$

$$x_2 = x_2^0 + z_2 = x_2^0 - \frac{z_5^2}{2x_2^0} + \dots,$$

$$x_3 = x_3^0 + z_3 = x_3^0 + \frac{x_3^0}{2x_2^0(x_2^0 - x_3^0)} z_5^2 + \dots,$$

$$y_1 = z_4 + \dots, \quad (15)$$

$$y_2 = z_5 + \dots,$$

$$L = L_0 + z_5 = L_0 + \frac{1}{2L_0} \left(\frac{x_3^0}{x_1^0} z_4^2 - \frac{x_1^0 x_3^0 - x_3^{02}}{x_2^{02} - x_2^0 x_3^0} z_5^2 \right) + \dots,$$

topiladi.

References:

1. "ROBOTOTEXNIK MEXANIZMLARNING MAXSUSLIKLARINI IZLASHDA MATRITSAVIY USULNING QO'LLANISHI" //Barotov Adizjon Sadiyevich, Abdullayev Sarvar Anvar O'g'li // Международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ». Выпуск №15 (том 2) (июнь, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.06.2021.
2. Брюно А.Д., Локальный метод нелинейного анализа дифференциальных уравнений // М.: наука, 1979.
3. "UCHBURCHAKLI GIDROSILINDIRIK MEXANIZMNI HOLAT FUNKSIYASINING MAXSUS NUQTA ATROFIDA ASIMTOTIK TASVIRLANISHI" //Baratova Mohira Abdalimovna, Abdullayev Sarvar Anvar o'g'li // Международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ». Выпуск №21 (том 2) (декабрь, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 31.12.2021.
4. Barotov A. S., Abdullayev S. A. "ROBOTOTEXNIK MEXANIZMLARNING MAXSUSLIKLARINI IZLASHDA MATRITSAVIY USULNING QO'LLANISHI" // International scientific and practical conference on "Modern problems of applied mathematics and information technologies", May 11-12, 2022, Bukhara, Uzbekistan.
5. Солеев А., Баротов А.С. Локальной представление в малой окрестности особой точки функции положения робототехнических механизмов // Узб.журн. Проблемы механики, 2000, № 3,-С. 4-8.
6. Солеев А., Баротов А.С. Локальной представление функции положения плоского механизма в окрестности особой точки // Узб.журн.Проблемы механики, 2000, № 6,-С. 13-18.